

REFERENCES AND RESEARCH TITLE	Assessment of European Policies for Decarbonizing Space Heating Systems in Existing Buildings		FINAL VERSION (Sept 2022 – Feb 2026)
REFERENCE REPORT	RT3A.05	TRL START	TRL END
		N/A	N/A
OVERALL OBJECTIVES	Identification of best practices and leading regions in space heating decarbonization across the EU, and development of guidelines to strengthen South Tyrol's decarbonization strategies.		
INTERNAL ACTORS	Edoardo Carangelo – EURAC; Flavia Trovalusci – EURAC; Dr. Dario Bottino Leone – EURAC; Dr. Simon Pezzutto – EURAC; Dr. Filippo Beltrami – EURAC; Prof. Dr. Alexandra Troi – EURAC; Dr. Wolfram Sparber – EURAC; Dr. Marc Zebisch – EURAC;		
METHODOLOGY	The research applies a qualitative methodology combining expert interviews, literature review, and comparative analysis. Interviews with experts in energy policy, climate action, and heating technologies provided insights into regulatory frameworks, policy effectiveness, and best practices. An extensive literature review was conducted combining academic studies, policy reports, and grey literature, integrated with data from the Odyssee-Mure Policy Mapper, IEA Policies Database, and EU Building Stock Observatory to identify patterns in space heating consumption and regulatory impacts. Finally, a comparative analysis of six EU frontrunner countries was carried out to evaluate and classify the impact of measures and policies.		
MOST RELEVANT PUBLICATION	An article titled 'A Comparative Policy Analysis of Residential Space-Heating Decarbonization in Europe: South Tyrol Case Study,' authored by all internal actors, is currently under review for publication in an open-access journal.		
EXTERNAL ACTORS AND STAKEHOLDERS	During the interview phase, professionals and experts from the following organizations were consulted: R2M Solution, the European Commission, Solar Heat Europe, Technische Universität Wien, Energy Cities, ifeu – Institut für Energie- und Umweltforschung, EuroHeat, the Energy and Climate Office of the Province of Bolzano/South Tyrol, IIECP (Institute for Energy Economics and Climate Policy), and the CEE Bankwatch Network.		
ACTIVITIES PERFORMED	In the initial phase of the project, a comprehensive analytical framework was developed through the combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. A total of 11 expert interviews were conducted, and approximately 300 policy instruments related to space heating decarbonisation were reviewed across the EU27. This evidence base was complemented by the systematic analysis of major European policy databases. Based on this review, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, and Sweden were identified as frontrunner countries in heating decarbonisation (Fig. 1). A comparative analysis was then carried out among these countries to examine differences in policy design, implementation approaches, and outcomes, allowing the identification of distinct patterns in policy effectiveness (Fig. 2).		
RESULTS ACHIEVED	The analysis highlights that mandatory standards deliver the strongest long-term impacts, as they ensure durable energy efficiency improvements and compliance through inspections and building codes. Financial incentives, particularly direct subsidies, emerged as the most widely used policy tool, providing substantial social benefits by helping households overcome high upfront investment costs. Fiscal instruments showed moderate effectiveness and proved most impactful when combined with stronger regulatory or financial measures. Furthermore, informative and training initiatives (including public awareness campaigns, energy advisory services, and One-Stop Shops) play a crucial role in addressing information barriers, fostering citizen engagement, and reinforcing the overall effectiveness of policy mixes. Overall, the results demonstrate that effective heating decarbonisation relies on policy layering, combining regulatory mandates, economic incentives, and educational measures within participatory and context-sensitive governance frameworks. Building on these findings, the project proposes the development of a roadmap for South Tyrol, starting with a thorough policy and technical assessment of the regional context (e.g., Fig. 3) to identify		

priority areas for intervention and key constraints. This diagnostic phase will inform the selection and sequencing of policy measures and ensure coherence with local conditions. The roadmap is designed as a replicable model, offering external validity for application in other regions. The proposed pathway begins with diagnostic and support measures, such as energy audits and the establishment of One-Stop Shops. This is followed by incentive-based and regulatory actions, including targeted subsidies, soft loans, and bans on fossil-fuel boilers in major renovations. A subsequent phase focuses on scaling up infrastructure, notably the expansion of district heating networks with mandatory connections in high-density areas. The final stage envisages the mandatory phase-out of traditional heating technologies, supported by robust compliance and enforcement mechanisms.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

After the project's completion, its results will support the development of a long-term policy roadmap for space heating decarbonisation in South Tyrol, grounded in the evidence and comparative analysis produced. The roadmap will inform future policy design and implementation processes and support strategic decision-making beyond the project's duration. The project's approach and analytical framework could be expanded and adapted to other geographical regions. In addition, a scientific paper based on the project results is currently under review for publication, contributing to the dissemination and consolidation of the project's findings at academic level.

IMAGES

Fig. 1) Frontrunner Countries in Space Heating Decarbonization

Fig. 2) Policy Type Effectiveness in Leading Countries

Fig. 3) Space Heating Systems in Renovated South Tyrol Buildings (Since 2010)